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Work Package 11
Education and Dissemination

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Project Deliverable

D11.2: Knowledge and Information Sharing Plan

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Executive Summary

The HEAP Knowledge and Information Sharing Plan will guide the implementation of the Education and Dissemination Work Package (WP11), which is being led by the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC), in collaboration with all partners of the HEAP consortium. The aim of Work Package 11 is to produce and disseminate knowledge and information about HEAP to project partners and the wider scientific community.

The Knowledge and Information Sharing Plan sets out the approach and activities to maximise the impact of the HEAP project through:

- Training and education activities for the HEAP target audience groups.
- Dissemination of the objectives and achievements of HEAP to its target audiences

Using best practices from previous EU projects, in particular the B3Africa biobanking project, the IARC's Learning and Capacity Building Branch will coordinate the planning and implementation of training activities (tutorials and online and on-site training sessions) to support data providers within the consortium to effectively upload data to HEAP, in compliance with the HEAP data model and the ethical and legal framework.

A key objective is to produce and disseminate learning and communications material to encourage and support European scientists beyond the consortium to use HEAP for research. This will promote the benefits of using HEAP, and build trust among policy-makers, civil society, and ethical and legal stakeholders, helping to secure a legacy for HEAP as a scientific resource.

As one of nine EU-funded projects in the [European Human Exposome Network](#), HEAP is committed to sharing results and outcomes within the network. This plan highlights a common, network-wide approach to Communication and Dissemination to maximise the impact of the projects' results and avoid duplication of effort.

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1 Introduction

The aim of Work Package 11, Education and Dissemination, is to produce and disseminate knowledge and information about HEAP to project partners and the wider scientific community.

The Knowledge and Information Sharing Plan (Deliverable 11.2) focuses on the following main areas of activity:

- Training and education activities for both project partners and future end users of the HEAP platform.
- Dissemination of the objectives and achievements of HEAP to its target audiences
- Communication with external stakeholders, with the other members of the European Human Exposome Network, and between project partners

The main sections in the documents are as follows:

Mapping of key topics – describing the objectives of the key areas of focus of the Education and Dissemination Work Package, including expected project impacts and key messages.

Mapping of target audiences – describing the stakeholder mapping activities and the main activities and messages for each target audience

Learning and informational resources – describing the plan for their elaboration and implementation

Learning and informational events – describing the plan for their elaboration and implementation

2 Mapping of key topics

2.1 Training and Education

Using best practices from previous EU projects, in particular the B3Africa project, the IARC's Learning and Capacity Building (LCB) Branch will coordinate the planning and implementation of training activities, as well as the production of training materials to support data providers within the consortium to effectively upload data to HEAP, in compliance with the HEAP FAIR data models and the ethical and legal framework.

The Training and Education element of HEAP will focus on the following areas:

Data privacy regulation, ethical and legal issues.

These training materials and events will promote discussion between HEAP project and [European Human Exposome Network \(EHEN\)](#) stakeholders, focusing on collaborative learning opportunities around this key topic, which is still evolving as the HEAP platform is being constructed.

Data harmonisation and curation – FAIR data principles

Training materials and events devoted to good practice in data management will be tailored to the learning needs of all academic researchers (whether using HEAP or not, although the HEAP platform will be used as an example), and will include Bring Your Own Data (BYOD) workshops and educational videos introducing FAIR principles.

HEAP Data Management and analysis services

Technical training in the use of the HEAP informatics platform, its features and benefits. These training materials and events will be tailored to the learning needs of HEAP data providers, in particular researchers uploading data to the platform and analysing data.

2.2 Communication and Dissemination

Communication activities will complement the Education and Training element of WP11 by promoting learning events and reporting on their outcomes.

A key objective is to produce and disseminate communications material to HEAP target audiences, to promote the project's aims and outcomes.

Building networks between professionals in the target audience categories to promote peer-to-peer learning is another key objective.

The Communication and Dissemination element of HEAP will be guided by the following priorities:

Key messages and target audiences

In consultation with the HEAP partners, key messages and communications channels and media will be adapted to each HEAP target audience in recognition of their differing requirements and motivations. Key messages and the level of priority accorded to each target audiences will evolve throughout the project.

The initial mapping of key messages is shown in the table below

Key message	Examples to illustrate key message	Target audience
Benefits to exposome research from using the HEAP platform	Sustainability plan for HEAP through the following use case examples: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Personal exposome profiling through wearable technology - Consumer cohort - Cohort data - Metagenomics and the internal exposome (biosamples, sequencing etc) - Combining these datasets for new insights 	Researchers (external to HEAP)
The importance of FAIR data principles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Importance of FAIR data principles when using the HEAP platform - Potential of HEAP for cohort data – getting more value out of these datasets 	All Researchers
Benefits of collaboration in scientific research and open science principles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Benefits and results of EHEN network project activities 	Researchers and policy makers
Promotion of the scientific concept of the exposome	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Benefits and results of EHEN network project activities 	All
Benefits to health from new technologies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Wearable sensors - Consumer data 	Public/wider citizens

Building an exposome research community

The potential for building networks between HEAP target audiences will guide planning and promotion of events and communication channels. The EHEN Communication and Dissemination Working Group provides opportunities for joint planning and coordination of activities to help achieve this goal.

3 Mapping of target audiences

The HEAP target audiences as set out in the HEAP proposal are shown in the table below:

Target audience group	Specific target audiences
Research	Data providers, Epidemiologists, Biologist/Medical researchers, Bioinformatics, Biobank managers, ICT scientists, Ethical experts, Applied AI users
Policy makers	National food agencies, National/international Environmental protection agencies, National and international public health agencies, Health organisations targeting cancer (WHO, IARC, NIH, NCI, EACR), Health organisations targeting maternity (WHO, IARC, Go-MCH)
Industry	Pharma, Food producers, ICT & electronics (IoT, wearable devices, mobile devices)
Public	Patient organisations. Civil society organisations and citizens

As the first step in designing appropriate Knowledge and Information sharing activities, the WP11 team began detailed target audience mapping in Year 1 of the project, based on the specific target audiences.

This exercise was started with the “Research” target audience group that will be the data providers and data processors for the HEAP platform.

HEAP personas

To engage this target audience, the WP11 team used a “Persona interview” approach to target audience mapping that is commonly used in marketing and product development.

The first round of Persona interviews with representatives of the “Research” target group and the “Public” target group were carried out during the first HEAP “Bring Your Own Data” workshop, held in December 2020. All those interviewed were from the HEAP partner institutions and involved in developing the HEAP platform.

The benefits of the “Persona interview” approach are:

- Enables learning materials and communications activities to be tailored to the needs of each target audience group, based on a clear understanding of their needs
- To promote team and network building between the HEAP project partners

HEAP target audiences – detailed mapping

Persona details/HEAP Work Package	Interaction with HEAP (data provider/data processor/system designer) and brief summary of learning needs
Epidemiologist Associated with the data cohorts in WPs 3,4,5, 8	Data provider. May need support in using AI.
Biologist/medical researcher Associated with the data cohorts in WPs 3,4,5, 8	Data provider. May need support in using AI.
Biobank manager -Associated with the data cohorts in WPs 3,4,5, 8	Data provider. May need support in using AI.
Bioinformatician WP 8 and 9 (Epigenomics, Microbiomics).	Data processor. Curates data, upstream processing.
Applied AI users Potentially all platform users. WPs 3,4,5, 8,9	Data processor. Refines algorithms/weighting for downstream data processing.
ICT scientist Associated with WPs 6, 10, 9.	-System designer/data processor. -No learning needs as will not be an end user of the platform. -Will contribute to the development of technical learning materials and events for data providers and processors.
Ethical expert. Associated with WP2 – Ethics and Regulations.	-System designer. -No learning needs as will not be an end user of the platform. -Will contribute to the development of Ethical/Legal learning materials and event for data providers and processors.
Public – citizen	-No direct interaction with the HEAP platform -Will benefit from the outcomes of HEAP

Detailed target audience mapping of the researcher, plus other HEAP stakeholder groups is planned to continue in 2022, with policy makers and the public a key focus.

Persona interview results are presented in Annex 1.

Learning Needs Assessment

In parallel with the Persona Interviews, the WP11 team conducted a Learning Needs Assessment Exercise with the specialist groups within HEAP, in particular those knowledgeable in the key topic areas identified in section 2.1. The Learning Needs Assessment sought to identify training needs of the target audiences by listing, per target audience group, the prerequisite knowledge and skills needed to be a competent user of the HEAP platform, and any related training requirements.

Members of the “Researcher” target audience (bioinformaticians) also contributed, to highlight their learning needs and expectation from the HEAP platform.

The benefits of the Learning Needs Assessment approach are:

- Highlights the expertise within the HEAP consortia available to develop learning materials
- Identifies the skills and knowledge required to become a competent user of the HEAP platform and predicts the learning needs of the HEAP target audiences
- Provides the information required to structure training materials

The table below shows the HEAP specialists and target audience groups who contributed to the Learning Needs Assessment.

HEAP partner/WP	Key topic specialism
MLC, WP 2 Ethics and Regulations	Data privacy regulation, ethical and legal issues
MUG, WP7 Data Interoperability and Sharing	Data harmonisation and curation – FAIR data principles
Logical Clocks, WP6 – Informatic platform and Knowledge Engine	HEAP Data Management and analysis services
CSC, WP10 – Secure infrastructure for Big Data	HEAP Data Management and analysis services (HEAP data processor)
University of Innsbruck, WP8, Epigenomics	Bioinformatics (HEAP data processor)
University if Warsaw, WP9, Microbiomics	Bioinformatics (HEAP data processor)

The results of the Learning Needs Assessment are in Annex 2 of this report.

4 Learning and informational resources

Learning resources

Following the Learning Needs Assessment exercise in 2020/2021, the learning resources to be delivered for each key topic area for 2022 are highlighted in the table below.

Key topic	Learning resources to be produced in 2022
Data harmonisation and curation – FAIR data principles	FAIR Video tutorials – short animated videos summarising the key principles of FAIR data. The aim of the HEAP “FAIR toolbox” video series is to provide an engaging way to support researchers or other future users of the HEAP platform to ensure their data is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable (FAIR) before upload. The target audience is academic

	<p>researchers, in particular, future data providers and users of the HEAP platform. The series will take a generic approach to FAIR best practice, using HEAP as a practical example.</p> <p>More information about this series is in Annex 4</p>
Data privacy regulation, ethical and legal issues.	Podcasts/recorded seminars from HEAP roundtables
HEAP Data Management and analysis services	Scope to be defined via mapping exercise (See Annex 3)

Scientific publications

- A HEAP marker paper is in draft form and will be finalised and submitted for publication in 2022.
- A further paper on the use of Personas for target audience mapping is also under preparation by the WP11 team at IARC, also planned for submission in 2022.
- WP 11 will coordinate the dissemination of scientific papers produced by the consortium, through the channels described below.

Communication/information channels

The table below shows the main external communication channels as developed and launched in 2020-2021, the approach to deploying these channels and their strategic purpose for promoting project goals.

Channel	Strategic approach	Strategic purpose
<p>HEAP website https://heap-exposome.eu/</p>	<p>-Provide key, publicly available project information</p> <p>-Provide access to learning resources via a learning platform linked to IARC learning</p> <p>-Later in the project, differentiate parts of the website by stakeholder group (public, policy maker, researcher etc)</p>	<p>-To serve as the main public face of the HEAP project, open to all audiences and delivering all the key messages of the project.</p> <p>-Able to evolve with the project, as new content becomes available and stakeholder groups evolve.</p>
<p>HEAP newsletter https://heap-exposome.eu/newsletter/</p>	<p>-Quarterly issue by email to a subscriber base</p> <p>-Focus is on people associated with the project and their work</p> <p>-Format includes one interview per issue, and a summary of exposome events and website news.</p>	<p>-Building engagement with the project through a “human interest” aspect</p> <p>-Subscribing to newsletter will build membership of the HEAP site ahead of the Learning Platform being populated</p>
<p>HEAP Twitter account https://twitter.com/heap_exposome</p>	<p>-Chosen in line with the other projects in the European Human Exposome Network, and because Twitter is widely used among the target audience in a professional capacity</p>	<p>-Network and engagement building with all key audiences</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Regular posts and retweets, planned in a content calendar, to provide ongoing updates on the project - The HEAP twitter account also appears in a feed on the home page of the HEAP website - Hashtags to be used in posts from the HEAP account and by project partners from their accounts: #exposome #HEAPproject #H2020 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Regular promotion of key messages and events on an ongoing basis - Involving project stakeholders with promoting HEAP
HEAP YouTube channel https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCvTOwwydTW4WcFO6b4kEcVg	Will host tutorial videos on legal/ethical, FAIR data and technical aspects of HEAP, and informational videos about the progress of the project and the HEAP partner activities (cohorts etc)	To support the building of an engaged exposome community
Zenodo https://zenodo.org/communities/heap-exposome/?page=1&size=20	Repository for technical reports and scientific papers on HEAP and the exposome	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Network building among a scientific audience -Collecting a body of research on HEAP and Exposome in one place
European Human Exposome Network website https://www.humanexposome.eu/	To serve as a common focus and source of information and news for all the projects in the network.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -To aggregate common information on the exposome -To reduce duplication of content across EHEN project websites -To amplify the common messages of all EHEN projects

During the development of the HEAP platform, two important internal communication channels are used:

- **GitHub:** <https://github.com/HEAP-EXPOSOME>. This is the source code repository and represents a way to collaborate and communicate for bio-informaticians, ICT and medical researchers.
- **Slack:** heap-workspace.slack.com

5 Learning and informational events

The main categories of events are listed in the table below:

Event type	Rationale	Benefits of this approach
“HEAP in 10” presentations and Q&A (standard presentation that can be added to, plus a Q&A format that is adaptable)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Presentations will be delivered by HEAP partners as part of on-line or in-person events, to different target audience -Format proven to be an effective vector of dissemination in previous research infrastructure projects, such as B3Africa (http://www.b3africa.org) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Easily adaptable to a range of events and audiences -Dissemination of key messages and of progress of the project -Collect feedbacks and comments from target audiences.
Scientific conferences: scientific papers /	Research results will be presented to the scientific community as publications in presentations, demonstrations, conferences,	-Improve awareness of HEAP within the wider “Researcher” target audience groups.

poster presentation and presentations booths	workshops and open access journals to maximize the accessibility. -All partners will contribute to these activities. Because of the COVID-19 pandemic, no physical booths to conferences could be organised. This activity will be covered by “HEAP in 10” presentations as a result of travel restrictions imposed by the COVID pandemic.	- Is expected to contribute to the HEAP sustainability plan
Human Exposome Assessment Roundtables	- 1-2 hour online workshop to be conducted on a regular basis - Focusing on one of the three main topics described above: Data privacy regulation, ethical and legal issues; Data harmonisation and curation – FAIR data principles ; HEAP Data Management and analysis services - Initially organised within the consortium (focusing on ELSI matters) in 2021, the roundtables will be open to a wider research community from 2022 onwards, targeting EHEN and beyond	-To develop thinking, gather feedback and encourage dialogue and joint decision making around key aspects of HEAP and exposome research -Network building and peer-to-peer learning
Bring Your Own Data workshops (BYOD)	- Proven to be an effective vector of dissemination in previous research infrastructure projects, such as B3Africa (http://www.b3africa.org) - The BYOD workshops will be dedicated mainly to HEAP users within the consortium, but invitations could be extended to other professionals from other initiatives or large-scale data resources. - This is a hands-on activity where researchers and stakeholders bring their data to test different components of the HEAP platform. BYOD activities have two main outcomes	-To test HEAP’s technical framework with research data from the consortium and from external researchers. This enables early engagement and collaboration, training, refining the solution and get effective feedback on the developed tools - Will allow development of a higher quality solution
HEAP Symposium “From Information to Action” (final year of the project, 2024)	-Stakeholders at all stages of the HEAP workflow (researchers, data providers, managers, analysts and curators, ethicists) will be invited to present on preliminary results and how their projects link to HEAP. - Policy makers will also be invited to present on their current challenges and expectations towards HEAP.	This will allow HEAP to be disseminated to a wider audience and consequently, to the sustainability of the platform.

6 Summary

Implementation

Key achievements in years 1 and 2 of the project

During the first 24-months of the HEAP project, the WP11 team has focused on developing, producing and disseminating communications

materials, establishing communications channels such as the European Human Exposome Network (EHEN) website, and the HEAP website and Twitter account, and on building strong working relationships with HEAP partners and the other EHEN projects.

All deliverables have been submitted according to the time plan, and the progress of the Work Package is in line with that set out in the HEAP proposal.

Deliverable 11.1, for the HEAP on-line platform and tools, was submitted in M6 of the project. In addition to this, HEAP WP11 also completed Deliverable 12.2, the development of the EHEN network website, and we will provide maintenance for the EHEN website throughout the project period.

Details and metrics for all the communication tools WP11 has produced over the first 24 months of the project are presented in the table below.

Comms tools and channels	Communication channels	Target audience	Monitoring indicators
Logo, corporate project identity	Via website, social media and communication materials	All	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HEAP logo and visual identity guidelines • EHEN logo and visual identity guidelines
On-line platforms, newsletters	https://www.humanexposome.eu	All	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 11k unique visitors since launch in March 2020. • 144,000 page views since launch
	www.heap-exposome.eu	All	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 197 visitors per month (based on May 2021) • 310 page views per month (May 2021) • 11 webposts https://heap-exposome.eu/news/
	HEAP newsletter	All	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Newsletters (Autumn 2020, Jan 2021, June 2021, August 2021). • 62 subscribers

	HEAP Zenodo community	Scientific (external)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 5 documents • 152 views • 89 downloads
Social media	HEAP Twitter account	All	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tweets: 123 • Followers: 949 • Tweet views: Average 5k per month <p>https://analytics.twitter.com/user/heap_exposome/home</p>

The first video in the HEAP video series has been released via The You Tube channel.

In the first 24 months of the project, the WP11 team has held inaugural/pilot sessions of training activities in three streams. These are – two **Bring Your Own Data workshops**, in collaboration with WP7, designed to collectively test and gather feedback on the platform as it is developed, **“Human Exposome Assessment” roundtable sessions**, designed to bring all WPs together to discuss and finetune the practical implementation of key aspects of the HEAP platform, and **“HEAP in 10” presentations**, designed to promote the HEAP project to the wider research community within the HEAP partner institutions.

The events are summarised in the table below:

Education and Dissemination events	Bring Your Own Data (BYOD) - on-line workshop (WP7)	HEAP consortia partners (internal)	1, 2-day workshop 22 attendees https://heap-exposome.eu/2020/12/22/collaboration-despite-covid-and-testing-times-for-the-fledgling-heap-platform/
	“Human Exposome Assessment” roundtable series #1: Ethics and regulations (WP2)	HEAP consortia partners (internal)	1 hour presentation combined with Q&A/discussion throughout 15 attendees
	“HEAP in 10” presentation (piloted at IARC science café)	Researcher (external)	10-minute powerpoint presentation of HEAP followed by Q&A, 70 attendees

<https://heap-exposome.eu/2021/02/18/heap-in-10-watch-this-short-presentation-for-an-overview-of-the-project/>

Community building (External): To support the material on the HEAP website, the HEAP e-mail newsletter was launched in November 2020, and is distributed quarterly. It contains a feature article on an aspect of the project (interview, partner institution profile etc) and is designed to build a HEAP community of learners and stakeholders. Subscribers to the newsletter are automatically have an account created on the HEAP website, which will host learning materials as the project progresses.

EHEN network: As well as leading the development and launch of the EHEN website, the WP11 team plays an active role in the EHEN Communication and Dissemination Working Group.

Delivery plan for year 3

The principal activities for year 3 grouped into the following categories:

- Scientific publications (WP 11 led)
- Learning resources preparation
- Events – organisation and communication activities
- Dissemination

The detailed WP11 plan for year 3 of the project is set out below in extracts from the on-line project plan (Asana.com).

Scientific publications

Aperçu Liste **Tableau** Chronologie Calendrier Tableau de bord Messages Fichiers

+ Ajouter une tâche

Nom de la tâche	Responsable	Échéance
HEAP marker paper (title, type of publication, I	ZK Zisis Kozlakidis	jan 3 2022 – mar 31 2022
HEAP persona paper	ZK Zisis Kozlakidis	avr 2 2022 – jun 30 2022

Learning resources preparation

ⓘ ☆ ○ Définir le statut

[Aperçu](#) [Liste](#) [Tableau](#) [Chronologie](#) [Calendrier](#) [Tableau de bord](#) [Messages](#) [Fichiers](#)

+ Ajouter une tâche

Nom de la tâche	Responsable	Échéance
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Learning resources for Ethics and Legislation 3	HC Heather Co...	fév 2 2022 – mai 31 2022
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Develop content and timetable for 2022-2023 series		fév 28 2022
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Hold event 1		avr 29 2022
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Hold event 2		jun 1 2022
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Produce HEAP FAIR toolbox videos	HC Heather Co...	Aujourd'hui – mai 26 2022
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Develop road map for technical training content	HC Heather Co...	mar 1 2022 – mar 31 2022

Events - organisation and communication activities

ⓘ ☆ ○ Définir le statut

[Aperçu](#) [Liste](#) [Tableau](#) [Chronologie](#) [Calendrier](#) [Tableau de bord](#) [Messages](#) [Fichiers](#)

+ Ajouter une tâche

Nom de la tâche	Responsable	Échéance	Priorité
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Organisation of HEAP Annual Meeting 2	HC Heather Coombs	jun 10 2022	Moyenne
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Define public talks programme		fév 28 2022	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Develop communication plan		fév 28 2022	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Organisation of BYOD workshops	TL Tracy Lignini	sep 30 2022	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Delivery of HEAP in 10 presentations	ZK Zisis Kozlakidis	jun 30 2022	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Development and delivery of HEAP rountables	HC Heather Coombs	déc 15 2022	

Dissemination ▼ ⓘ ★ ○ Définir le statut

Aperçu Liste Tableau Chronologie Calendrier Tableau de bord Messages Fichiers

+ Ajouter une tâche ▼

Nom de la tâche	Responsable	Échéance	Priorité
▼ Content calendar			
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Monthly website post	HC Heather Co...	jan 28 2022 ↻	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tweets per web post	HC Heather Co...	jan 28 2022 ↻	
Ajouter une tâche...			
▼ HEAP newsletter			
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> HEAP newsletter Jan 2022	HC Heather Co...	jan 3 2022 – jan 31 2022	Moyenne
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> HEAP newsletter Apr 2022	HC Heather Co...	mar 2 2022 – avr 29 2022	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> HEAP newsletter July 2022	HC Heather Co...	mai 17 2022 – jul 15 2022	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> HEAP newsletter Oct 2022	HC Heather Co...	sep 6 2022 – oct 31 2022	
Ajouter une tâche...			
▼ HEAP flyer (as per task 11.4)			
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Produce HEAP leaflet flyer as per the HEAP proposal	HC Heather Co...	avr 2 2022 – mai 26 2022	Moyenne
Ajouter une tâche...			
▼ HEAP and EHEN websites			
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Restructure to focus better on distinct target audiences	HC Heather Co...	nov 30 2022	Moyenne

Key tasks for years 4 and 5

Key tasks for the final two years of the project include:

- Delivery of Knowledge and Information Sharing Plan
- Monitoring of reach to target audiences and adjustment of strategy as required
- Communication and dissemination of final results
- Organisation of HEAP symposium
- Contributing to the sustainability plan for HEAP

7 References

Sources

Persona interview approach:
<https://www.openlawlab.com/wp-content/uploads/2014/09/Design-Process-Tool-Persona-Document-Margaret-Hagan.png>

Annex 1 – Persona interview results (anonymised)

HEAP personas - Epidemiologist #1

	<p>INTERESTS</p> <p><i>Defining research questions.</i></p> <p><i>Discovering the potential of the data provided in HEAP to their area of research.</i></p> <p><i>Collaborating with relevant colleagues to access and analyse the data.</i></p>	<p>ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS</p> <p><i>Will work on real data, therefore they will have ethical / ELSI considerations</i></p>
<p>HEAP Stakeholder group: <i>Epidemiologist</i></p> <p>Profession: <i>Epidemiologist</i></p> <p>Learning Needs Assessment category: <i>Data provider/data processor/end user</i></p> <p>Age range: <i>40-50</i></p>	<p>POWERS / EXPERTISE</p> <p><i>Typical educational background is: Medical doctor with specialisation in epidemiology</i></p> <p><i>Can define research questions</i></p> <p><i>Has a vision of how the data can be used</i></p> <p><i>Can apply for and receive grant funding.</i></p>	<p>NEEDS</p> <p><i>Access to data for new projects</i></p> <p><i>To work with existing data sets to get new insights and to achieve their research objectives</i></p> <p><i>Access to the expertise of a data analyst and others to help them achieve their research goals</i></p> <p><i>May not need to directly interact with the platform, (unless with data science background).</i></p>

HEAP personas - Epidemiologist #2

	<p>INTERESTS</p> <p><i>Formulating and answering research questions</i></p> <p><i>Accessing data to answer these research questions</i></p> <p><i>Interested in data analysis, secure management and Dissemination in connection with research projects</i></p> <p><i>Particular interests can include maternity cohort data, wearable sensors and HPV vaccination cohorts, and collaborating with other research teams working with this data.</i></p>	<p>ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS</p> <p><i>-Ethical and governance requirements associated with data cohorts.</i></p> <p><i>- Ownership of data, eg by national governments and national laws governing their use.</i></p> <p><i>-Process of obtaining permits for secondary use of health and social data, eo through Findata https://www.findata.fi/ - the Finnish Health and Social Data Permit Authority.</i></p> <p><i>-Setting up the IT system to allow users to access their data, but not on their own premises.</i></p>
<p>HEAP Stakeholder group: <i>Epidemiologist</i></p> <p>Learning Needs Assessment category: <i>Data provider/data processor/end user</i></p> <p>Profession:</p>	<p>POWERS / EXPERTISE</p> <p><i>Typical specialisms include metagenomics and epidemiology.</i></p> <p><i>Has access to cohort data and the ability to define research questions</i></p>	<p>NEEDS</p> <p><i>A connection to Machine Learning technologies</i></p> <p><i>A better understanding of how to use the HEAP platform for Deep Learning analysis.</i></p> <p><i>To understand how consumer data, and clinical medical</i></p>

<p><i>Medical geneticist,</i></p> <p>Age range: 40-50</p>	<p><i>Has access to research funding.</i></p>	<p><i>information can be analysed together to gain new insights</i></p> <p><i>Continuing input and support from colleagues in a collaborative working spirit</i></p>
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HEAP personas - Biologist/Medical researcher #1

	<p>INTERESTS</p> <p><i>Typical interests include:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Formulating and answering research questions. -Coordinating bioinformatics pipelines. -Metagenomics and Next Generation Sequencing (NGS). -Providing interoperable cohort data to researchers in the spirit of open science. -Accessibility of data analytics pipelines for scientists who are not IT specialists -Engagement of civil society - making the case for funding, and encouraging the public to consent to their data being used. 	<p>ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS</p> <p><i>Would need to follow laws and regulations pertaining to HEAP data (actual rules determined by ethicists/lawyers/project management).</i></p>
<p>HEAP stakeholder group: <i>Biologist/Medical researcher</i></p> <p>Learning Needs Assessment category: <i>Data provider/data processor/end user</i></p>	<p>POWERS / EXPERTISE</p> <p><i>A typical professional profile could include expertise in molecular biology and bioinformatics, as well as experience in handling related data in a research context.</i></p>	<p>NEEDS</p> <p><i>A very simple and user-friendly interface through which to access HEAP.</i></p> <p><i>The ideal “starting pack” for HEAP - short videos about the platform.</i></p> <p><i>Explaining the concept of exposome in practice (using the</i></p>

<p>Profession: Molecular biologist, Research coordinator</p> <p>Age range: 40 -50</p>	<p><i>Has access to HEAP data through the HEAP data administrator.</i></p>	<p><i>partners projects) → also useful to the general public, and demonstrating the social value of the research.</i></p> <p><i>Learning more about the other work packages/ projects and teams in HEAP and the EHEN, their working methods and challenges.</i></p>
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HEAP personas - Biologist/medical researcher #2

	<p>INTERESTS</p> <p><i>Using data to answer research questions.</i></p> <p><i>Prevention of disease incidence and progression.</i></p> <p><i>How to use raw consumer data in research, and the potential and limitations of this data.</i></p> <p><i>Combining consumer data with other data sources such as metagenomic and registry data.</i></p>	<p>ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS</p> <p><i>Works with real data, which has ethical, legal and social implications (ELSI) considerations</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>-How to protect individuals from being identified/traced through personal data</i> <i>-How to secure consent from users to access their data</i> <i>-GDPR</i> <i>-National laws on consent and on use of consumer and shopping data</i>
<p>HEAP stakeholder group: <i>Biologist/Medical researcher</i></p> <p>Profession: <i>Medical doctor. Public health specialist, epidemiologist. Project manager.</i></p> <p>Learning Needs Assessment</p>	<p>POWERS / EXPERTISE</p> <p><i>Has and can provide access to consumer data.</i></p> <p><i>Can identify new opportunities for the design and application of consumer data to research questions.</i></p> <p><i>Can provide training and expertise in applying consumer data to existing data cohorts.</i></p>	<p>NEEDS</p> <p><i>To know how to use the HEAP platform to:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>-Implement new approaches to data analysis, including new analytical frameworks</i> <p><i>Training needs:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>-Programming, machine learning models (basic knowledge)</i> <i>-Using “Plug and play” solutions, ready-made analysis pipelines.</i>

<p>category: <i>Data provider/data processor/end user</i></p> <p>Age range: 30-40</p>	<p><i>Conceptualising new uses for consumer data in health care - such as apps where consumer profile data and medical data are entered, and the app users receives tailored health advice.</i></p> <p><i>May also have IT skills, such as R programming, and additional skillsets such as Data impact assessor.</i></p>	<p><i>Collaborating with others who have similar data/challenges and interests.</i></p>
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HEAP personas - Biologist/Medical researcher #3

	<p>INTERESTS</p> <p><i>The link between external exposures and health outcomes, in particular relating to precision health (including preventative actions) and precision medicine.</i></p> <p><i>Typical interests could include - how external exposures may affect the health of pregnant women and their infants, in the context of a particular data cohort.</i></p>	<p>ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS</p> <p><i>Works with real data, which has ethical, legal and social implications (ELSI) considerations.</i></p> <p><i>Works with anonymised/coded data, does not see any participants names, and is not involved in recruitment to cohorts.</i></p>
<p>HEAP stakeholder group: <i>Biologist/Medical researcher</i></p> <p>Profession: <i>Postdoctoral scientist.</i></p> <p>Learning Needs Assessment category: <i>Data</i></p>	<p>POWERS / EXPERTISE</p> <p><i>Typical specialisms include Pharmacology/toxicology.</i></p> <p><i>Depending on role and research project, can provide access to data - eg from wearable sensors.</i></p> <p><i>Depending on role and research project, can identify</i></p>	<p>NEEDS</p> <p><i>To understand the legal and regulatory implications and practicalities of conducting an international research project (between EU and non-EU countries) using sensor data and devices.</i></p> <p><i>This includes, where to store/host the sequencing</i></p>

<p><i>provider/data processor/end user</i></p> <p>Age range: 30-40</p>	<p><i>new opportunities for the design and application of data, e.g. from wearable sensors and devices, in a research context.</i></p> <p><i>Further expertise could include: Personal exposure monitoring schemes, the data that they generate and the interpretations that can result. Next Generation Sequencing (NGS) technologies and mass spectrometry to profile personal exposures.</i></p>	<p><i>data before, during and after analysis, practicalities of data transfer.</i></p> <p><i>Protocols and guidelines for uploading data in Hopsworks.</i></p>
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HEAP personas - Biologist/Medical researcher #4

	<p>INTERESTS</p> <p><i>Typical research interests could include: national registry data, cancer registry data. As a specific example - seasonal levels of Vitamin D and the impact of supplement policies introduced in Finland in 2003 and 2010.</i></p> <p><i>Would like to increase awareness of specific data cohorts, eg the Finnish Maternity cohort data and sample-related data.</i></p> <p><i>Interested in discovering how data from several cohort studies could be combined for enhanced analysis.</i></p>	<p>ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS</p> <p><i>National data contexts - for example, Findata offers a remote access environment (supported by CSC) for secure data processing. From May 2021 all data processing that utilizes national health registers or combines health and social data from different data controllers will be centralised through Findata.</i></p>
<p>HEAP Stakeholder group:</p>	<p>POWERS / EXPERTISE</p>	<p>NEEDS</p> <p><i>Video tutorials on how to use the platform.</i></p>

<p><i>Biologist/Medical Researcher</i></p> <p>Profession: <i>Research coordinator.</i></p> <p>Learning Needs Assessment category: <i>Data provider/data processor/end user</i></p> <p>Age range: <i>40-50</i></p>	<p><i>Can advise how to request samples and data from cohorts they are working with.</i></p> <p><i>Can advise how to request permission to obtain data from national registries, and be the point of contact for managing requests.</i></p> <p><i>A typical academic background is: university degree in Biochemistry, Phd in Immunology, studying for a Masters degree in Statistics.</i></p> <p><i>A typical area of expertise is reproductive health.</i></p>	<p><i>To understand how HEAP could be useful for particular research questions. To see examples of real data being processed by HEAP, such as, for example, Vitamin D manuscripts.</i></p> <p><i>Having an informal/formal platform for knowledge exchange within the Consortia and across work packages.</i></p> <p><i>Understanding the publishing rules within the network and within the consortia.</i></p>
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HEAP personas - Bioinformatician #1

	<p>INTERESTS</p> <p><i>Epigenomics and understanding environmental effects on health. Areas of focus include diet, nutrition etc.</i></p> <p><i>Longitudinal changes in the epigenome and how that impacts health.</i></p> <p><i>Interested in how data will be stored, and in the informed consent process.</i></p>	<p>ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS</p> <p><i>May have prior knowledge of ethics, for example from writing ethics applications for biobanks, researching information from ethics committees, researching standards, etc.</i></p> <p><i>Aware of sensitivities of genetic data. If data is centralised, aware that data will need to be anonymised.</i></p>
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<p>HEAP stakeholder group: <i>Bioinformatician</i></p> <p>Profession: <i>Post-doctoral scientist</i></p> <p>Learning Needs Assessment category: <i>Data provider/data processor/end user</i></p> <p>Age range: <i>20-30</i></p>	<p>POWERS / EXPERTISE</p> <p><i>A typical academic background is: Molecular medicine with a Phd in Neuroscience.</i></p> <p><i>Typical areas of expertise include: genomics and molecular biology.</i></p> <p><i>Has expertise in bioinformatics, which could also include industry experience, such as working in precision diagnostics.</i></p> <p><i>May already be using Machine Learning in the course of their current role.</i></p>	<p>NEEDS</p> <p><i>More information and training on the Hopworks platform. Video introduction and tutorials.</i></p> <p><i>More in-depth/practical aspects of legal and ethical. GDPR, practical application.</i></p> <p><i>Practical workshops where researchers can work jointly on analysing. (BOYD)</i></p> <p><i>Collaboration with other data cohorts to understand their work and common challenges.</i></p>
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HEAP personas - Bioinformatician #2

	<p>INTERESTS</p> <p><i>General interests include:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>-Statistical computations for survival data</i> <i>-Data modelling for cancer screening</i> <p><i>HEAP: Inference vs prediction with regards to research questions. Which research questions will use inference, and which prediction?</i></p>	<p>ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS</p> <p><i>Needs to understand and comply with data protection rules relating to national registry data</i></p>
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<p>HEAP stakeholder group: <i>Bioinformatician</i></p> <p>Profession: <i>Biostatistician</i></p> <p>Learning Needs Assessment category: <i>Data processor</i></p> <p>Age range: <i>50-59</i></p>	<p>POWERS / EXPERTISE</p> <p><i>Has access to health registry data.</i></p> <p><i>Makes an impact on government policy through data modelling work.</i></p> <p><i>Can input to training material/programmes in biostatistics.</i></p>	<p>NEEDS</p> <p><i>To improve programming skills in Python and Java.</i></p> <p><i>Access to statistics for multiple comparisons (for multiple sources of data, in particular rich sequencing data).</i></p> <p><i>As a biostatistician, needs to work in collaboration with Bioinformaticians.</i></p>

HEAP personas - Bioinformatician #3

	<p>INTERESTS</p> <p><i>Defining research questions and using bioinformatics tools to run data analysis.</i></p> <p><i>Using HEAP bioinformatics tools and creating new pipelines to answer research questions with HEAP data.</i></p>	<p>ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS</p> <p><i>Will work on real data, and this work has Ethical, Legal and Societal Issues (ELSI) considerations.</i></p>
		<p>POWERS / EXPERTISE</p>

<p>HEAP stakeholder group: Bioinformatician</p> <p>Profession: Bioinformatician</p> <p>Learning Needs Assessment category: Data processor</p> <p>Age range: 30-40</p>	<p><i>A typical educational profile is: Biologist before completing further training in bioinformatics</i></p> <p><i>Has access to data and can define research questions</i></p> <p><i>Can provide IT-related training on how to use various bioinformatics tools</i></p>	<p><i>Simple, efficient user interface to analyse data with simple tools.</i></p> <p><i>Clear guidance and tutorials</i></p>
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HEAP personas - ICT scientist #1

	<p>INTERESTS</p> <p><i>Designing and building interoperable IT tools that can be combined with each other.</i></p> <p><i>Designing simple IT tools for data providers (non-IT specialists) to use.</i></p>	<p>ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS</p> <p><i>Needs to understand the legal and ethical implications (e.g. GDPR), and take these considerations into account while developing IT solutions.</i></p> <p><i>Does not handle real data in the course of his job.</i></p>
<p>HEAP stakeholder group: <i>ICT scientist</i></p> <p>Profession: <i>Software developer</i></p>	<p>POWERS / EXPERTISE</p> <p><i>A typical educational profile is: university degree in computer sciences, software engineering etc.</i></p>	<p>NEEDS</p> <p><i>To understand the needs and requirements of the future users of HEAP.</i></p>

<p>Learning Needs Assessment category: <i>System designer</i></p> <p>Age range: <i>30-40</i></p>	<p><i>System analysis and software tools development: gathering requirements from different user groups (both user and application side).</i></p>	<p><i>To understand the level of IT knowledge and experience level of the future users of HEAP.</i></p> <p><i>Training on Hopsworks is needed, both for users and for backend technicians.</i></p>
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HEAP personas - ICT scientist #2

	<p>INTERESTS</p> <p><i>Programming, to translate users' requirements into a software solution.</i></p> <p><i>Working with biological data/human samples</i></p> <p><i>Analysing human samples through bioinformatics.</i></p> <p><i>To integrate different software tools into the platform, data processing, knowledge discovery.</i></p>	<p>ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS</p> <p><i>When developing tools we usually use mock data, but we need to bear in mind that real data will be used once the software is completed.</i></p> <p><i>"Real life data" requirements must be considered in the design of the software and the workflow. Need to bear in mind the physical location of the server (e.g., within EU, outside EU) where the data will be processed and stored.</i></p> <p><i>When dealing with human samples, we need to be aware that this is sensitive data.</i></p>
<p>HEAP Stakeholder group: <i>ICT scientist</i></p> <p>Profession: <i>Software developer</i></p>	<p>POWERS / EXPERTISE</p> <p><i>Has access to an on-site computing</i></p>	<p>NEEDS</p> <p><i>To understand users' requirements in relation to the data, and understand the nature</i></p>

<p>Learning Needs Assessment category: System designer Age range: 30-40</p>	<p><i>cluster with Hopsworks installed.</i></p> <p><i>Has experience of designing IT systems, and knowledge of different programming languages, Python, Java, and programming frameworks.</i></p> <p><i>Has knowledge of Hopsworks and bioinformatic pipelines for processing data.</i></p>	<p><i>of the data they will be bringing to HEAP.</i></p> <p><i>Exposure to bioinformatics techniques.</i></p> <p><i>Exercises/ examples of practical Machine Learning.</i></p> <p><i>To use Machine Learning to discover knowledge/inferences from real data.</i></p>
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HEAP personas - ICT scientist #3

	<p>INTERESTS</p> <p><i>Developing efficient software tools for Next Generation Sequencing (NGS)</i></p>	<p>ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS</p> <p><i>No specific ethical and legal challenges. Develops tools and often works on mock-up data.</i></p>
<p>HEAP stakeholder group: <i>ICT scientist</i></p> <p>Profession: <i>Academic/Software developer</i></p> <p>Learning Needs Assessment</p>	<p>POWERS / EXPERTISE</p> <p><i>Typical educational background: Physicist before specialising in ICT science.</i></p> <p><i>Can provide access to a High Performance Computing (HPC) cluster</i></p>	<p>NEEDS</p> <p><i>More knowledge about Hopsworks and its functionalities.</i></p> <p><i>Access to detailed information from bioinformaticians, such as pipeline usage with sample data, and examples of specific research questions.</i></p>

<p>category: <i>System designer</i></p> <p>Age range: 50-60</p>	<p><i>that could be used to run analysis pipelines.</i></p> <p><i>Can provide IT-related training: Hadoop/Spark technologies, as well as Python and Java programming.</i></p>	<p><i>To work in collaboration with bioinformaticians.</i></p>
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HEAP personas – Public. Citizen

	<p>INTERESTS</p> <p><i>Personal and family health, how to treat illnesses, preventative measures etc.</i></p> <p><i>How to participate in health research as a citizen, contributing personal health data, both following invitations, or during a routine medical visit.</i></p> <p><i>Gaining insights into health from research.</i></p>	<p>ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS</p> <p><i>Is concerned about being personally identified following participation in a data cohort. Needs reassurance on data anonymization.</i></p> <p><i>Is concerned about how personal data can be used in the future, following participation in a data cohort. Legal and regulatory framework regarding this.</i></p>
<p>HEAP stakeholder group: <i>Citizen</i></p> <p>Profession: <i>Any</i></p> <p>Learning Needs Assessment category: <i>End user</i></p>	<p>POWERS / EXPERTISE</p> <p><i>Can consent to participate in a data cohort, by giving consent for existing data to be used, providing new data (e.g., through questionnaires), or giving consent to use and/or</i></p>	<p>NEEDS</p> <p><i>To understand their legal rights and the process of consent in providing their data.</i></p> <p><i>To understand how communication works with data cohort participants. For example, are there regular</i></p>

Age range:
30-40

providing biological samples.

Can take part in a community of participants and ongoing activities related to data cohort studies.

Can educate themselves about data protection rules and the value of data cohort studies to science and society.

cohort participants gatherings or communications? How are the results of the research programmes communicated to participants?

To understand the value of the policy and social outcomes of research programmes using data cohorts, and the importance of the role of the citizen

Annex 2: Results of Learning Needs Assessment

Work package 2 - Ethics and regulations		
Stakeholder/audience group	Prerequisite knowledge/skills	Related training requirements
HEAP internal stakeholders. ICT scientists (WP6, 7 and 10)	Already knowledgeable as a part of their role in developing the HEAP platform. HEAP Ethics and regulations WP2 actively works with them. This was done during development of the Data Management Plan.	No training needed. This group could work with WP2 to develop Ethics and Regulations training materials
EHEN project partners (ICT scientists, Data providers, data processors)	Basic knowledge of data protection and privacy issues	No training needed. Possible synergies with developing training materials for the other projects. Would be interesting to compare their models of data governance. This subject could be covered as part of the EHEN Ethics Working Group.
HEAP internal stakeholders. Data providers, data processors (WP3,4,5, 8, 9)	Basic/intermediation knowledge of data protection and privacy issues	Seminar/presentation about general overview of GDPR, key terms, to set out the context. Content would include: Data protection, GDPR. A background, and why compliance is importance. Could be a simple presentation or a recorded seminar. Could be delivered by MLF member from WP2 and a Data protection officer from one of the partners, such as CSC. MLF could do 10 mins, GDPO 10 mins, Q&A could last 10 mins. Could run an event within the consortia to begin with.
HEAP internal stakeholders. New Ph.D. students/new joiners with no experience of data protection issues (Work Package Leads should identify them). Data providers, data processors. (also ICT scientists?)	We should assume a limited knowledge of data protection and associated legislation.	Need basic training to become more effective in their role as data providers and data processors. Survey to assess levels of knowledge, followed by 2-hour session on GDPR. Background slides would be the same as for HEAP internal stakeholders, but with more detail, and a longer Q&A. Software tools would need to be covered as well.

<p>"Sustainability" group, consisting of new end users (from 2024 once HEAP becomes an open resource), including policy makers and general public.</p>	<p>For this group, we assume no prior knowledge of legal and ethical matters to do with data protection</p>	<p>Ethics and Legislation (WP2) training proposal (Developed using source material: Deliverable 2.1: Legal mapping and DPIA) Training course: "An overview of data protection, ethics and governance within HEAP" Target audience: Researchers before using HEAP. No prior knowledge of HEAP required.</p> <p>1. Introduction:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The HEAP platform – main components (Entitlements Management System, Submission Engine, Information Commons, Knowledge Engine, Data and Feature Warehouse) - The legal context – GDPR etc - The ethical context - Overview of data governance in HEAP. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Who is affected by data governance? (this should describe the target audience for the training and why are they concerned) o Principles: necessity and proportionality of data processing in HEAP: e.g. de-identification, data minimisation measures <p>2. The HEAP data lifecycle:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Overview of how data moves through the platform, where the approval points are, controls etc (picking up the main components as previously described). Areas to be covered include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Data protection / anonymisation policies and measures for the metadata catalogue, feature store and possible other functions of the warehouse o Security (including encryption) standards and assurances for all different kinds of data, including REMS <p>3. Data Governance Framework</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - FAIR data principles - Roles and responsibilities in data governance: Data sources, Data custodians, Data processors - The role of the HEAP Data Access Committee (DAC) - Access and use procedures (role-based access control) - Retention periods and policies - HEAP controller/processor framework agreement - HEAP Data subjects' rights policy - Data protection of software and code deployed by researchers on the HEAP platform
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		<p>4. Data governance in action: Local approvals and per-project data protection measures - Examples of how to adapt HEAP Data governance rules to particular projects, use cases (ie adjusting if other instances of platform components are added at other institutions)</p> <p>5. Data governance in action : International transfers - Data sharing beyond the European Economic Area, challenges and legal solutions - Use case overview – wearable sensors, Finnish use cases</p> <p>6. Further reading and sources of information and advice - Tbc, overview of useful sources</p>
WP6 - Informatics platform and knowledge engine		
Stakeholder/audience group	Prerequisite knowledge/skills	Related training requirements
Data Owner/Controller(s) e.g., PI	No programming skills reqd. Need domain knowledge of how the data can be used. (need more specific)	Need to learn to how give different types of access (read-only, read-write, etc) to users to data. Learn how to use CSC services(Authorization/REMS).
Data Stewards/Curators	No programming skills reqd. Need domain knowledge of the data that they are curating.	Need to understand how to design metadata templates for artifacts (files, tables, features). Need to udersatnd how to start jobs and analyze (high level) the results. Learn how to use CSC services(SDA uploading/access).
Data processors - Bioinformaticians	Can program (Python). Domain knowledge of bioinformatics.	Need to learn to use Jupyter notebooks and the Hopsworks platform to manage data and libraries. May need to learn to write workflows (Airflow). Learn how to use CSC services (SDA uploading/access).
Data Engineering - Bioinformaticians	Can program (Python). Domain knowledge of bioinformatics. Work with large volumes of data, so need to	Need to learn how to store and process large volumes of data. Learn how to use CSC services (SDA uploading/access). May need to learn data parallel programming (Spark)

	learn data parallel programming (Spark).	
Machine Learning - Bioinformaticians	Can program (Python). Domain knowledge of bioinformatics. Use machine learning to build predictive models.	Need to learn how to train models, evaluate models, and deploy/use models. Learn how to use CSC services (SDA uploading/access).
System Administrator	Knows Unix/Linux operating system and how to manage servers and software.	Installation and configuration of Hopsworks and CSC resources. Learn how to use CSC services.
WP7 - Data interoperability and data sharing		
Stakeholder/audience group	Prerequisite knowledge/skills	Related training requirements
Data providers	FAIR principles . An awareness of what is in the platform (data catalogue), platform governance when requesting access to data	<p>FAIR data management</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -HEAP Self-Assessment Service (SAS) -FAIR principles and metadata standards -Hopsworks and CSC tools -FAIR toolbox Apps <p>Trusted repositories</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -what is a trusted digital repository (together with CSC) -Introduction to HEAP cohort catalogues -dSpace / Fair Data Points <p>DMP updates</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -lifestyle cohort (Martin) -metadata catalogues <p>(source: WP7 presentation at HEAP Annual Meeting)</p>

All		How to use communication channels for the consortium (incl. social media, tweets/writing stories, etc...) / communication guidelines. How to use Zenodo (to upload press releases, YouTube videos, guidance)
WP8 - Epigenomic analysis		
Stakeholder/audience group	Prerequisite knowledge/skills	Related training requirements
Data Providers. (These are current WP8 team members, including epigenomics researchers, bioinformaticians)	Will need practical training on aspects of the HEAP platform, in particular WP2 Ethics and Regulations, WPs 6 and 10 relating to Hopsworks and the secure IT infrastructure.	Knowledge sharing events with other WPs. At some stage, they would be interested in sharing information with WP9 (Metagenomics) to find out what they are doing. Learning material on legal aspects of data protection and security, focusing on the risks and ethics/regulations around putting data sets on open access databases due to the risks of identifying individuals.
Data users/end users. (These are likely to be researchers on the epigenome, bioinformaticians, ageing researchers, environmental researchers, mathematicians, biologists. Later on, policy makers and the general public).	The end product would be bioinformatic algorithms, and the end goal is to make a tool to assess the exposome's impact on individuals. Examples of policy impacts would be - eg: for a motorway in a narrow valley, what would be the air and noise pollution's impact on the epigenome. The knowledge gap here would be in how to use the algorithm to assess the impact on the epigenome. (what are we expecting in terms of prerequisite knowledge)	Training would be on algorithms (e.g., tutorials. What is the prerequisite knowledge to use the algorithms?), what they are and how to apply them. Will need to be designed in a user-friendly way? e.g., Breast cancer risk algorithm - are publicly available. Could be available to the public. This would be relevant towards the end of the project.

WP9 - Metagenomics analysis		
Stakeholder/audience group	Prerequisite knowledge/skills	Related training requirements
Data Providers. (These are current WP9 team members, including metagenomics researchers, bioinformaticians)	WP9 members have required skills and data to complete the WP8 research but will need practical training on aspects of the HEAP platform, in particular WP2 Ethics and Regulations, WPs 6 and 10 relating to Hopsworks and the secure IT infrastructure.	Knowledge sharing events with other WPs. At some stage, they would be interested in sharing information with WP8 (Epigenomics) to find out what they are doing. Learning material on legal aspects of data protection and security, focusing on the risks and ethics/regulations around putting data sets on open access databases due to the risks of identifying individuals.
Data users/end users. (These are current WP9 members as well researchers on the metagenomics, bioinformaticians, ageing researchers, environmental researchers, mathematicians, biologists).	The end product would be bioinformatics pipelines run on the Hopsworks infrastructure, and the end goal is to make a tool to assess the exposome's impact on individuals. The knowledge gap here would be in how to use the pipelines and how to assess the impact on the genomics.	Training would be on pipelines, what they are and how to apply them. Hopsworks should provide user friendly interface to manage and run pipelines. This would be relevant towards the end of the project.
WP10 - Secure infrastructure for big data		
Stakeholder/audience group	Prerequisite knowledge/skills	Related training requirements
Data Owner/Controller(s) (e.g., PI)	No programming skills reqd. Need domain knowledge of how the data can be used.	Need to learn to how grant different types of access (read-only, read-write, etc) to users to data. Learn how to use CSC services(Authorization/REMS).

Data Stewards/Curators (Data providers)	No programming skills reqd. Need domain knowledge of the data that they are submitting and how to structure it.	Learn how to use CSC services(SDA uploading/access) and how to upload data and structure it into datasets so that correct permissions are allocated.
System Administrator (ICT scientist)	Knows Unix/Linux operating system and how to manage servers and software.	Installation and configuration of CSC resources and possibly Hopsworks. Learn how to use CSC services and Hopsworks.
Data processor (ICT scientist)	Can program Python, R and Machine learning and AI. Are able to clean and analyse data.	Need to learn Hopsworks and analyse data.
Software developer	Software development, non-specific to HEAP.	Probably no training required. CSC Services APIs provide integration between CSC Services and Hopsworks.

Annex 3: Mapping exercise for training material - HEAP Data Management and analysis services

WP10: Existing training content (HEAP researchers target group):

Content title	Description	Target audience/level of prior knowledge required	Format eg (documentation, video tutorial, workshop)	Current location
SD-Connect	Detailed information about SD service used for data upload	Users of CSC services / No prior knowledge required	documentation, video	https://docs.csc.fi/data/sensitive-data/sd_connect/
SD-Desktop	Detailed information about SD service used for processing data in a secure environment	Users of CSC services / No prior knowledge required	documentation, video	https://docs.csc.fi/data/sensitive-data/sd_desktop/
SD Services	YouTube Playlist of videos found in docs.csc.fi	Users of CSC services / No prior knowledge required	video	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wbSf9wR305A&list=PLD5Xtevf3yGtuatGnWmvh39j12lefyp9

Planned training content for exposome researchers/HEAP (future)

Content title	Description	Target audience/level of prior knowledge required	Format eg (documentation, video tutorial, workshop)	Proposed location (if known)
Workshop on CSC SD Services	- Setting up your private workspace with SD services - Accessing data using SD Desktop	HEAP researchers / no prior knowledge required	workshop	online some time end of Q1

Annex 4: Development of FAIR toolbox videos

The source material for the video series was gathered during the second Bring Your Own Data (BYOD) workshop, in October 2021. The workshop included a “Scripting” stream, where data providers presented real-life examples of challenges they have faced and resolved in preparing data for upload to the HEAP platform. The concept art work and scripts was prepared in liaison with a science communication agency.

Annex 1: Concept art for the FAIR frog and the Data Gator

FAIR FROG

DATA GATOR

DATA GATOR

Annex 2: Video script for the FAIR toolbox overview video

Title	FAIR data principles and the exposome - Introduction
Runtime	5 minutes

Item	Visuals	Narrative / VO	Time
1	<p>Fair frog sits on a lily pad in a bayou, dressed in a pristine lab coat. Stands up, clears throat, and starts speaking formally.</p> <p>The nose of the Data Gator approaches ominously and dips under the water.</p>	<p>FAIR: Hello and welcome to the first in a series of short videos about FAIR Data principles and scientific research.</p> <p>I'm the Fair Frog, and...</p>	30 secs

	<p>The Data Gator rises out of the water underneath the lily pad, the Fair frog on their head.</p> <p>Fair frog hops off Data's head and starts again. He adjusts lab coat, pulls out a checklist and starts talking, as if giving a lecture.</p> <p>Data rubbing head, interrupts FAIR</p> <p>FAIR sighs and folds up checklist</p>	<p>DATA: Sorry, I didn't see you there, Fair!</p> <p>(To the camera) ... and I'm the Data Gator! Nice to meet you!</p> <p>FAIR: So... I am the FAIR frog and I'm here to tell you about FAIR data, and how it can help us improve the way we work. Firstly...</p> <p>DATA: FAIR data? Sounds like a bit of a headache to me!</p> <p>FAIR: OK. Come with me Data, I think I'd better show you...</p>	
2	<p>Fair frog hops from his lily pad into a lab, Data follows him, dripping wet, and pulls on a crumpled lab coat.</p> <p>FAIR frog addresses the viewers</p> <p>Data knocks over several test tubes, picks them up, looks muddled.</p> <p>Data holds the test tube up to his snout and discovers elements inside the test tube and his eyes get bigger.</p>	<p>FAIR: (speaking more naturally) What's one thing that all researchers have in common? We all need to find, share and reuse data!</p> <p>FAIR frog to the audience: But sometimes, and especially when the Data Gator is around, that's not as easy as it sounds!</p> <p>Academic research offers more knowledge-sharing opportunities than ever before. There's so much potential for new discoveries, insights and collaborations.</p> <p>But if we want to see the benefits, we all need to make sure our research data is easy to work with.</p> <p>FAIR frog to Data Gator: Here are those results you asked for.</p>	40 secs

	<p>Fair frog picks up a printout that was next to the test tubes.</p> <p>Hands the printout to Data Gator who looks at it then looks at the test tubes, and scratches his head.</p> <p>Data blushes, embarrassed. He surreptitiously bins the paper and throws a lab coat over the pile of test tubes</p>	<p>DATA: Are you sure these are the right results? Or maybe these are the wrong samples? Er...</p> <p>FAIR: If you're not sure, how can anybody else be sure?</p> <p>DATA: Er, and what were you saying earlier? Something about data? I'm listening now...</p>	
3	<p>Fair frog hops over the word FAIR.</p> <p>Each word from the acronym FAIR animates on screen.</p> <p>Data Gator yawns and picks up the word 'Reusable' and walks away from FAIR...</p> <p>Fair frog rolls his eyes</p>	<p>FAIR principles help make sure research data is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable.</p> <p>For you, for me, and for anybody else who might want to work with it one day.</p> <p>When data is FAIR, it can be easily collected, connected, linked and integrated with other datasets – to provide insights for other researchers.</p> <p>FAIR: Where are you taking that word, Data?</p> <p>DATA: I'm reusing it! It could come in handy!</p>	30 secs
4	<p>Fair frog is back in the lab. There's a large video screen in the lab. The HEAP logo is on the screen.</p>	<p>Let's take a look at FAIR data principles in action. Let's take exposome data as an example. It can come from Personal Exposome Monitors, consumer receipts, or patient records. It can also come from biological samples.</p> <p>Imagine if we could use computing power to analyse all these different types of data, and share them between research projects!</p>	25 secs

		I think it's time to meet Roxana, the Project Manager of the Human Exposome Assessment Platform	
5	FAIR frog interviews Roxana	<p>FAIR: Hi Roxana! Tell us about your project!</p> <p>Roxana: Introduces the HEAP project, mentions a few cohorts, and the objectives of the project. project</p> <p>FAIR: Why are FAIR data principles important for a project like this?</p> <p>Roxana: HEAP makes it possible to share data and analysis tools to produce knowledge about the impact of the exposome on human health.</p> <p>This can only be achieved by sharing high-quality data that is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable.</p> <p>FAIR: How can researchers be sure that their data is FAIR?</p> <p>Roxana: We have developed a FAIR data Self-Assessment Service, to help researchers check if their data is FAIR. It's available online as a checklist. Once researchers have completed the checklist, they get a report, highlighting areas that need further work.</p> <p>FAIR: Thank you Roxanna, fascinating!</p>	2 mins
	<p>Screen walkthrough of the Self-Assessment Service, checking the boxes, pressing send.</p> <p>Screen shows radar diagrams show up from the report</p>		
6	<p>In the bayou - Data hands out pieces of paper labelled 'RESEARCH' to passing dragon flies.</p> <p>Fair Frog takes the remaining research papers from Gator and puts it inside a folder with a padlock on it.</p>	<p>FAIR: So does following the FAIR principles mean that anyone can access and reuse your data? The answer is no.</p> <p>Data can be private, or only shared under certain restrictions, and still be FAIR.</p>	30 secs

	<p>FAIR frog zaps the paper held by the dragon fly with their tongue, puts it inside the folder.</p> <p>Data pulls the word reusable out of his pocket and sticks it onto the folder.</p>	<p>And some open data may not be FAIR, if it doesn't have a clear reuse licence, for example.</p> <p>I think you need reminding about reuse licences Data!</p>	
7	<p>Fair Frog and Data Gator stand side by side in the bayou. Key text words bubble up in the bayou: Discover, store, manage, reuse</p> <p>Data takes a bite out of a document.</p>	<p>Remember, the FAIR principles are designed to help us understand how to discover, store, manage and reuse your data – for the benefit of everyone.</p> <p>DATA: I'm going to watch the other videos on each of the Fair principles. It'll help when I CRUNCH those numbers! Come with me!</p>	20 secs
8	<p>Optional extra scene if video hosted outside the HEAP learning platform</p> <p>www.heap-exposome.eu</p>	<p>FAIR: Visit the HEAP website for more information about how you can use the Fair principles in your research, and to access the Self-Assessment Service</p>	15 secs